

III СЕКЦИЯ

ИҚЛИМ ЎЗГАРИШИНИНГ ТАБИЙ ГЕОГРАФИК ВА ИҚТИСОДИЙ-ИЖТИМОЙ МУАММОЛАРИ, УЛАРИНГ ЕЧИМЛАРИ

ПРИРОДНО-ГЕОГРАФИЧЕСКИЕ И ЭКОНОМИКО-СОЦИАЛЬНЫЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ ИЗМЕНЕНИЯ КЛИМАТА, ИХ РЕШЕНИЯ

NATURAL, GEOGRAPHICAL, AND SOCIO-ECONOMIC ISSUES RELATED TO CLIMATE CHANGE AND THEIR SOLUTIONS

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EVALUATING NATURAL-ECOLOGICAL AND HYDROLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF WATER RESERVOIRS FOR SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT: A CASE STUDY OF THE SARSANG RESERVOIR, AZERBAIJAN

Abstract: *This study analyzes the key natural-ecological, hydrological, and energy-production characteristics of the Sarsang Reservoir and its surrounding area, with particular focus on the Sarsang Hydropower Plant (SHHP). The authors employed a comparative-geographical method to analyze and correlate relevant parameters of major reservoirs in the Republic of Azerbaijan. Core geomorphological and bioclimatic parameters of the study area were calculated. For the first time, the De Martonne's bioclimate index was applied to assess the territorial suitability from a bioclimatic perspective. Based on the research findings, recommendations have been proposed within the framework of a Coastal Ecosystem Management Plan (CEMP).*

Key words: *Sarsang Reservoir, Republic of Azerbaijan, De Martonne's bioclimate index, CEMP, sustainable development, SGD-13, SDG-14*

Introduction. The restoration and reconstruction of the liberated territories of the Republic of Azerbaijan, alongside the repatriation of displaced populations to their ancestral lands and the promotion of sustainable economic development in the Karabakh and Eastern Zangezur economic regions, represent key strategic objectives of the “I State Program on the Great Return to the liberated territories of the Republic of Azerbaijan” (Program).

Addressing these issues necessitates the implementation of ameliorate measures and the modernization of irrigation infrastructure. The reservoir is also expected to play a pivotal role in enabling sustainable resettlement and fostering economic development in the newly established settlements in its vicinity. Beyond supporting agricultural expansion, the area also presents considerable potential for tourism development.

Considering the above, the research studied the impact of natural and ecological conditions on the population return and settlement process and the development opportunities of various economic sectors in the Sarsang Reservoir and surrounding areas in the Aghdara District, and prepared proposals for socio-economic development. The favorable natural and geographical conditions and resources of the region make intensive settlement and economic development (agriculture, tourism, light industry, etc.) relevant here.

Study of the research area. The average annual water reserves of rivers originating in the liberated territories are estimated at approximately 2,295 million cubic meters, with nearly 46% (1,049 million cubic meters) derived from transit rivers. These reserves can diminish by up to 50% during arid years, underscoring the critical need to assess the hydro-ecological status of existing reservoirs and optimize their management. Such measures are vital for ensuring reliable access to potable and irrigation water and for enhancing the utilization of alternative energy sources in the region.

Analysis and discussions. The Sarsang Reservoir, constructed on the Tartar River in 1976, has a volume of 575 million cubic meters and a dam height of 125 meters (**Figure 1**). Prior to the

occupation, it supplied irrigation water to approximately 100,000–120,000 hectares of agricultural land across six administrative districts – Aghjabadi, Aghdam, Barda, Goranboy, Tartar, and Yevlakh. The Sarsang Hydroelectric Power Plant (Sarsang HPP), integrated into the reservoir complex, initially had a generation capacity of 50 megawatts and an average annual production of 123.0 million kWh. The complex comprises an earthen dam, a multi-purpose discharge system for both irrigation and energy, and an operational water outlet structure [2].

Figure 1. Main hydrotechnical parameters of the Sarsang Reservoir

Table 1.

The largest reservoirs in the Republic of Azerbaijan by area, surface and volume, production capacity of HPP and settlement in border districts

№	Reservoir	Area, km ²	Surface, km ²	Volume, km ³	Average multi-year PC of HPPs, million kWh	Population living in border districts, thousand people
1.	Mingachevir Reservoir	605	464,43	15,730	1 400	392,5
2.	Shamkir Reservoir	116	89,93	2,680	810	394,3
3.	Araz Reservoir	145	96,39	1,254	148	208,5
4.	Yenikand Reservoir	23,2	20,44	1,580	343	276,0
5.	Sarsang Reservoir	14,2	10,65	0,575	123	57,0

Based on the data from [6, 9]

The area of the Sarsang Reservoir is 14.2 km², and the surface is 10.65 km² (Azercosmos, 2024). The reservoir is surrounded on both sides (north and south) by mountain slopes forming a deep narrow valley and covers a 13–14 km section of the Tartar River valley.

The average multi-year discharge of the Tartar River, which flows directly into the Sarsang Reservoir, is 684.4 million m³. The area of the Tartar River’s catchment basin is 2,650 km² (Figure 2) [7, 14]. Snow (31%), rainfall (13%) and underground (56%) sources participate in its nutrition. According to its chemical composition, the waters of the Tartar River belong to the carbonate class and have a mineralization degree of 150–300 mg/l [3].

The Sarsang Reservoir exhibits a convex configuration along the right bank of the Tartar River, extending approximately 13–14 kilometers in length and varying in width from 2.5 to 500 meters [7]. Its irregular shoreline, characterized by numerous indentations and protrusions, spans a total length of 66 kilometers. Owing to its complex geographical setting and terrain structure, the Sarsang Reservoir is considered among the most technically challenging reservoirs globally. Situated at an elevation of approximately 700–720 meters above sea level, the area presents significant hypsometric elevation.

This topographic positioning substantially elevates the risk of catastrophic failure in the event of structural or operational disruption (Figure 3) [1, 10].

Figure 2. Tartar River catchment and study area

Figure 3. Digital elevation model (DEM) of the Sarsang Reservoir catchment area

The complexity of the coastline allows for the organization of various types of economic activities on the shoreline of the reservoir. Thus, there are numerous capes washed by water on three sides, especially in the north of the reservoir. These areas have high attractiveness, creating conditions for the development of various types of tourism and water sports [11, 15].

The climate of the Aghdara District, where the Sarsang Reservoir is located, belongs to the temperate hot desert type, characterized by mild winters and dry hot summers. The average annual temperature is 12–14°C. The hottest months are July-August. During this period, the average monthly temperature is 26°C, and the maximum temperature is 40°C. The coldest month is January, with an average monthly temperature of 1.6–2.5°C. The average annual rate of atmospheric precipitation is 370 mm. The wind regime is seasonal, with an average wind speed of 3–4 m/s (3 points on the Beaufort scale). [12, 13]

Sarsang Reservoir belongs to the group (type) of reservoirs located in the river valley (channel). According to R. Hejikhovsky’s classification of reservoirs by surface area and volume, Sarsang Reservoir is included in the small (by surface area, 20–2 km²) and medium (by volume, 1–0.1 km³) groups, respectively. In the classification of reservoirs by depth in Azerbaijan, it is the only reservoir in the “very deep” ($H > 100$ m) category. The greatest depth of the reservoir (H_{max}) is 103.0 m, and the average depth is 40.8 m [14].

Graph 1. Annual water discharge of the Tartar River (m³/sec)

Sarsang Reservoir belongs to the group of perennial and quickly developed ($A = 64.00$ m) reservoirs due to its regulation nature. The average perennial discharge of the Tartar River, the main river flowing into the Sarsang Reservoir, is 684.4 million m³, and the peak period falls in spring and early summer. The largest tributaries of the Tartar River, Agdabanchay and Levchay, play an

important role in its nutrition (Graph 1). The level regime of the Sarsang Reservoir is typical for a mountain reservoir. The filling of the reservoir begins in April, during the period of high-water levels of mountain rivers, and lasts for 3 months. The level decreases during intensive water use in July-August. The rest of the year, the water level in the reservoir is stable. During the operation period, the level change in the reservoir is 0.12–0.17 m [10].

The depth range of the Sarsang Reservoir (between the most distant points) is 44 m, the profile length is 8.07 km, the reservoir volume is 575 million m³, of which 500 million m³ is usable volume, the average width (B_{average}) is 1.72 km, and the coastline development coefficient is 5. The minimum height of the reservoir above sea level is 678 m, and the maximum height is 722 m. Thus, the Sarsang Reservoir is located on average 700 m above sea level. The average slope of the reservoir is in the range of 1.7–4%, and the maximum slope is in the range of 15.9–23.7%.

To study the natural and ecological conditions around the Sarsang Reservoir, De Martonne's bioclimate index (IDM) was calculated for the area in question in accordance with the international methodology (Formula 1) [5, 8]:

$$IDM = \frac{P}{T + 10}$$

Formula 1. De Martonne's bioclimate index (IDM)

Here P is the average annual precipitation, in mm; T is the average annual temperature (in °C). According to the data of the Tartar Meteorological Station, the minimum annual precipitation for the areas surrounding the Sarsang Reservoir is 363 mm, and the maximum annual precipitation is 602 mm. The annual absolute minimum of the air temperature is –17°C, and the annual absolute maximum is +40°C. If the De Martonne's bioclimate index (IDM) for the Sarsang Reservoir and its surrounding areas is found based on the annual average amounts of precipitation and temperature, it will be in the form of $IDM = \frac{363}{13.9+10}$. In this case, the De Marton bioclimatic index (IDM) for the Sarsang Reservoir and its surrounding areas is 15.2 [8]. According to the accepted international classification (*Pasarella et al.*), areas in the interval $10 \leq IDM \leq 20$ are classified as semiarid (less unfavorable) zones, and the soils of these areas need regular irrigation.

At the same time, the continentality coefficient of the climate was determined (Formula 2):

$$K = \frac{A * 100}{0,33\varphi}$$

Formula 2. Continentality coefficient of the climate

Here A is the average annual amplitude of air temperature; φ is the geographical latitude of the area. According to the formula, $K = \frac{25+100}{0,33+40} = 189,4$. According to the accepted international classification, the climate is considered moderately continental if $165 \leq K = 189.4 \leq 205$.

Considering the parameter, the reconstruction of the irrigation infrastructure and collector-drainage system is of great importance for the development of sustainable settlement and agriculture in the Sarsang Reservoir and surrounding areas [11].

Local agri-climatic conditions are more favorable for growing wheat, corn, and sunflowers, as well as for horticultural and fruit-growing farms. In addition, it is possible to grow barley and legumes. The high-water supply of the study area expands the possibilities of using water for both drinking and irrigation purposes.

Results. As part of the scientific research aimed at examining the natural-ecological conditions of the areas surrounding the Sarsang Reservoir and evaluating their influence on sustainable settlement patterns and the development potential of various economic sectors, a comprehensive analysis was conducted. This included an assessment of the natural-geographical characteristics of the reservoir and its adjacent territories, an evaluation of the current ecological state, and the identification of promising directions for economic development. These assessments were made in accordance with the functional-genetic classification of settlement types, considering local natural-climatic factors, bioclimatic potential, and agrophenological traits.

As part of the study, an adapted Coastal Ecosystem Management Plan (CEMP) was developed for the Sarsang Reservoir, incorporating internationally recognized methodologies and best practices.

The plan is structured into eight comprehensive stages, each integrating critical aspects of ecological assessment, infrastructure development, economic diversification, and sustainable resource management. The CEMP addresses foundational ecological conditions, tourism and aquaculture development, environmental protection, innovation, community involvement, and monitoring and evaluation. The stages are summarized as follows:

1. Analysis and planning

- a) Conducted a hydroecological and biochemical assessment of the Sarsang Reservoir.
- b) Investigated local biodiversity and assessed the aquaponics potential of the water body.
- c) Developed a measurable, multi-criteria management framework for the reservoir and its surrounding areas.

2. Infrastructure development

- a) Reconstructed and verified hydrotechnical infrastructure associated with the reservoir.
- b) Restored and networked road, communication, and public service infrastructure in alignment with Coastal Ecosystem management Plan (CEMP) targets.
- c) Implemented soil stabilization, dam reinforcement, afforestation, and other mitigation measures to reduce vulnerability to natural hazards and extreme events.

3. Tourism development and management

- a) Established recreational zones and tourism clusters to support local hospitality and service industries.
- b) Promoted ecotourism and developed infrastructure for water-based recreation, outdoor, and adventure tourism.
- c) Introduced sustainable tourism practices, regulated visitor capacity, and formulated a marketing strategy for tourism products.

4. Fisheries and aquaculture programs

- a) Supported sustainable fisheries, introduced moratorium zones, and defined protected water areas to facilitate ecological regeneration and community entrepreneurship.
- b) Provided agri-technical consultancy and SME support to promote aquaculture initiatives and the development of a regional brand identity.
- c) Introduced sustainable aquaponics practices, cultivated promising aquatic species, and implemented protective measures for aquatic ecosystems.

5. Environmental protection and restoration

- a) Rehabilitated coastal ecosystems and introduced sustainable management strategies.
- b) Enforced protective regulations for ecologically sensitive zones, implemented waste disposal and recycling initiatives.
- c) Ensured species-specific habitat preservation and established periodic ecological monitoring systems.

6. Innovation initiatives and research

- a) Conducted scientific research on coastal ecosystem dynamics, climate variability, and aquatic biodiversity.
- b) Fostered collaboration between scientific institutions and industrial stakeholders for sustainable environmental infrastructure (SEI), renewable energy solutions, and ecosystem-based adaptation approaches.
- c) Promoted local entrepreneurial innovation in areas such as aquatic biotechnology, ecotourism, and sustainable aquaculture through venture support systems.

7. Public participation and community development

- a) Encouraged active participation of local communities in ecosystem governance and decision-making processes.
- b) Organized community-based environmental education, capacity-building workshops, and training programs.
- c) Facilitated communication between NGOs, local communities, and government bodies, and developed a targeted action plan for community development.

8. Monitoring and evaluation

- a) Assessed progress toward predefined CEMP success indicators using clear evaluation criteria.

- b) Involved local stakeholders in environmental assessment processes.
- c) Promoted accountability and transparency through public dissemination of environmental status reports and data.

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ХУДУДНИ ОҚИЛОНА ТАШКИЛ ЭТИШДА ИҚЛИМ ОМИЛИ ВА ТАРИХИЙ АНЪАНА (БУХОРО ШАХРИ МИСОЛИДА)

Аннотация. Мақолада чўл зонасида жойлашган Бухоро шаҳрида рўй бераётган иқлимий (ҳароратдаги тебранишлар, шамол ва бошқ.) ҳодисалар, уларнинг шаҳар ижтимоий ва иқтисодий салоҳиятини белгилашдаги аҳамияти, шаҳар фаолиятини оқилонга ташиқил этишининг анъанавий ва замонавий шакллари баён этилган. Шаҳар ҳудудида атмосфера ёгинларидан фойдаланиш орқали яшил майдонлар ҳиссасини ошириши, ободонлаштириши ишлари сифатини яхшилаш, пировард натижада шаҳар микроиқлимини яхшилаш бўйича тавсиялар берилган.

Калит сўзлар. шаҳар ҳудуди, атмосфера ёгинлари, ҳовуз, қудуқ, оқилонга ташиқил этиши,